

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE HISTORY OF MEDICINE

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Annotation. This article reflects on the stages of development of the history of medicine, and provides information on the research conducted within this discipline.

Keywords: trend, methodology, medical deontology, medical practice, social principle, humanities, empirical research, didactic opportunity.

Scientific and technical progress and the emergence of modern technologies, as well as the discovery of new diagnostic methods and treatment of diseases, have enriched medicine so much that, as a result, modern medicine has emerged instead of the "healing art" that existed in it hundreds of years ago. However, if we look at the history of medicine, in ancient times, doctors tried to identify diseases in the early stages, to find their cause, and most importantly, to prevent the disease by taking preventive measures (donosology) and changing the way of life.

Doctors of ancient and ancient times attached great importance to psychosomatic dependence, mood and mental health to maintain physical health. Studying the history of the formation and development of medicine helps not only to expand the level of mastery, but also to connect the modern knowledge system with the ancient historical system, and in some sense, using the laws of dialectics, to look into the future.

Studying the history of medicine plays a key role in the cultural, aesthetic, ethical, and professional development of modern doctors. Medical art is not only passing information from generation to generation, but also joining the system of religious, philosophical, and national knowledge with the goal of perfecting humanity.

The development of the history of medicine as a science can be conditionally divided into three periods:

The first period is related to the collection and collection of data in the medical world. It is the most continuous period from the time of Hippocrates to the present, and it is related to the collection of information on medicine and the provision of medical care in a broad sense in all directions.

Many works on the history of medicine appeared in Shark during the Middle Ages. The life of Abu Bakr Ar-Razi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Sharafuddin Ilaki, Najibuddin Samarkandi, Ismail Jurjani and other famous doctors in Central Asia in the work of scholars such as Abu Hassan al-Bayhaqi, Ibn al-Kifti, Ibn Abi Usaybia, Abu Bakr Ibn al-Khalikon and interesting information and evidence from their activities are presented. However, such works are few and scattered, so they cannot be considered a system of sciences in the field of medical history.

In the second period (from the 18th to the 19th century), the study and discussion of the collected data was systematized. In this period in Germany

K. Springl, W. Undirlich, G. Pushman, Yu. Pagel, A. Girsh, E. Litre from France, Sh. The Darambers were creative in this field.

In Russia, F.G. Politkovsky, Ya.M. Works on the history of medicine were created by researchers such as Govorov.

The third period is related to the formation of the first "History of Medicine" departments in higher educational institutions and the formation of the history of medicine as a separate discipline. In 1894, the first cafe of the history of medicine was opened at the medical faculty of Moscow University.

The first lectures on the history of medicine in the Central Asian republics were given by specialists in various fields of medicine. For example, in 1930, G.M. Semenov, the head of the "Histology and Embryology" department, taught the history of medicine at the Samarkand Medical Institute. In 1940, these lectures were given by P.M.Faktorovich, head of the "Biology" department.

The first "Chair of the History of Medicine" in Central Asia was opened on March 1, 1948 at the Tashkent Medical Institute. Later, similar departments were opened in other universities of Central Asia.

In 1957, a team of historians of medicine was established in Uzbekistan. In the 1950s and 1980s, the study of the history of medicine gained wide scope. A group of great scientists appeared, including A.A.Abdullaev, M.Kh. Kadirov, M.M. Makhmudov, I.K.Abdullaev.

Proponents of the religious-mystical theory put forward the idea that man came into existence, that he was healthy and healthy from the beginning, but due to his inaction, he suffered suffering, disease and death. The appearance of the first hospitals and medical schools is associated with the development of churches and mosques. Therefore, supporters of the materialist theory see medicine as a response to environmental influences. As Hippocrates wrote: "Life itself forced people to seek and discover the art of medicine." The improvement of medicine is mainly due to the increase of human knowledge, the development of science and

technology.

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